

HISTORY OF ENGLISH WRITING DOCUMENTS IN THE MIDDLE AGES

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Abstract: This article represents history of writing In the Middle Ages. On that time, they only the educated elite could read and write. Nevertheless, the English government and legal system relied on written evidence. Many of the surviving medieval documents record the acquisition of land, the resolution of disputes, the payment of money, and the rights and responsibilities of individual people: things, which it was important for people to know and prove. Other documents record the cultural life of the Middle Ages. Bibles, prayer books, service books and works of pious instruction remind us of the central role of the Catholic Church. However, many literary works are secular, and intended for entertainment. Until the invention of the printing press in the fourteenth century everything was hand-written.

Key words: manuscripts, fiction, literature, handwriting, style, reading.

ИСТОРИЯ АНГЛИЙСКИХ ПИСЬМЕННЫХ ДОКУМЕНТОВ В СРЕДНИЕ ВЕКА

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена история письменности в средние века. В то время читать и писать умела только образованная элита. Тем не менее, английское правительство и правовая система полагались на письменные доказательства. Многие из сохранившихся средневековых документов фиксируют приобретение земли, разрешение споров, выплату денег, права и обязанности отдельных людей: вещи, которые людям было важно знать и доказать. Другие документы фиксируют культурную жизнь Средневековья. Библия, молитвенники, богослужбные книги и произведения благочестивого наставления напоминают нам о центральной роли Католической Церкви. Однако многие литературные произведения носят светский характер и предназначены для развлечения. До изобретения печатного станка в четырнадцатом веке все писалось от руки.

Ключевые слова: рукописи, художественная литература, почерк, стиль, чтение.

INTRODUCTION

This unit explores a number of features of medieval documents, including their layout, the languages in which they were written, authentication devices to persuade readers of the document's genuine nature, and marks of ownership across the centuries. There is a brief introduction to handwriting styles and abbreviations used in the Middle Ages, and finally a set of interactive paleography exercises to test your skill in reading medieval English documents. Throughout the unit, illustrative images are taken from the collections held by Manuscripts and Special Collections at the University of Nottingham.

These surprisingly famous works of fiction, then, stimulated the feelings and received the passionate devotion of all literate lessons of Spain, from the wonderful Emperor Charles V himself to the lowliest clerk in his service. Even the ordinary dependancy of twentieth-century.

English-speaking readers to detective novels is hardly ever comparable, for the reading public of the early sixteenth century, a whole lot more credulous and uncritical than that of later generations, surrendered itself to these knightly memories with an abandon now seldom experienced through mankind without in childhood. The pages of this chivalric fiction have been thumbed with an enthusiasm amounting to a passion, and their fascination spurred the illiterate to

master rapidly the artwork of reading. In the royal palace and in the humblest hut these novels had been read, often aloud, so that a completely unlettered target audience should experience vicariously the reputedly actual and historical experiences of noble heroes. The aristocracy of each and every shade and degree, which include its women kind, and even the clergy, devoted much of their sufficient enjoyment to this diverting pastime.

THE MAIN PART

This popular devotion to the popular fiction is absolutely reflected in the present day protests of moralists and the prohibitory law of the mid sixteenth century and later in opposition to the "lying histories" which bump off so much time of youths and maidens, particularly, and stimulated them to ape so slavishly the manners, habits, and speech of imaginary heroes and heroines. Indeed, the allegedly wicked younger generation, and some of its elders, regarded to choose the dubious ethics and dubious codes of chivalry to the sterner doctrines taught by using the Church. Mothers who left their daughters at home locked in their rooms for security from the risks besetting their advantage have been only exposing these damsels to corruption and imperiling their everlasting salvation, for it too frequently passed off that the young female occupied themselves at some stage in this incarceration with reading secreted copies of chivalric novels. And regularly as not the mother herself study them, brazenly or clandestinely.

Even earlier than the look of the posted model of Amadis of Gaul, a partiality for similar mild reading existed in the perfect social spheres. Pious Queen Isabella was once acknowledged to have in her fortress at Segovia a scroll replica of a chivalric tale *Historia de Lanzarote, which was once in all likelihood the Demanda del Sancto Grial con los maravillosos fechos de Lanzarote y de Galaz*, first printed in 1515 after her death. But it was once her illustrious grandson, Charles V, who genuinely fell underneath the sway of this literature. His imperial enthusiasm for the knightly *Belianis de Grecia*, it is said, caused its writer to write a sequel, and a comparable work in French used to be translated into Castilian verse at the Emperor's command. And when this titular head of the Holy Roman Empire abdicated the throne of Spain, he took into retirement with him one or greater of these chivalric narratives. Nor used to be he unique amongst European monarchs in this fondness for romantic fiction, even though his responsibility may additionally have been large for the fondness of his royal prisoner, Francis I of France, for these books, whom he appears to have delivered to them. A later French king, Louis XIV, and William the Silent have been also among the royalty who succumbed to their charm.

The favor of princes encouraged the diffusion of chivalric literature among their topics and inspired the translation of these Spanish novels into more than a few languages of Europe, for that reason making them available to the literate instructions everywhere. The statesmen and diplomats of politically dominant Spain sought leisure from the heavy strain of their obligations through reading such fiction lots as their counterparts in a later age discover short-term launch in detective mysteries. One of the most distinguished diplomats of sixteenth-century Spain, Don Diego Hurtado de Mendoza, whilst journeying to Rome as ambassador, took copies of *Amadis of Gaul* and the *Celestina* as his solely books on the journey. The informant complains that this dignity appeared to derive extra proposal from these contrasting works of leisure than he did from the Epistles of St. Paul. The catalogue of Ferdinand Columbus, the titled son of the discoverer of America, indicates that he had many early variations of these romances in the prosperous library that he assembled. A distinguished humanist, Juan de Valdés, properly recognised in courtly circles, who additionally went to Italy, confessed in his well-known *Diálogo de la lengua* that he had spent ten of the high-quality years of his existence in palaces and courts where he did now not

employ himself "in any exercising more virtuous than in analyzing these falsehoods," which gained such electricity over him that when he picked up a extra decent work he was once in no way in a position to end analyzing it. He had firsthand expertise of most of the romances of chivalry of his time and, in his judgment, Amadis of Gaul, Palmerín and Primaleón had been the first-rate written.

People of distinction with a passion for the modern-day literary fashion have been by no potential constrained to the secular factors of society. Although the clergy railed at the great studying of the novels of chivalry, many of their personal number, including some renowned for their piety and mysticism, had been addicted, at least briefly, to this worldly vice, as a few ruefully admitted later. Ignatius Loyola, founder of the Jesuit Order, used to be accustomed to peruse such "vayne Treatises" and asked for them to relieve the tedium of convalescence from a damaged leg suffered at the siege of Pamplona in 1521. Under the influence of some anxious journey it appears possibly that this splendid saint's early enthusiasm for the lofty codes and romantic idealism of the knights of chivalry was transferred to the vastly profounder idealism of the Founder of Christianity, consequently spiritualizing the chivalric ideal. Indeed, one literary critic asserts that Loyola's militant Jesuits have been a type of knight-errantry a lo divino .

Santa Teresa's sixteenth-century biographer, Francisco de Ribera, sought to exonerate her from this girlhood peccadillo by means of maintaining that it used to be the Devil who prompted her to read such literature. He provides that she spent an awful lot time in this way and "... her wit was so outstanding and ... she imbibed their language and style so properly that, inside a few months, she and her brother, Rodrigo de Cepeda, composed a novel of chivalry full of journey and imagination, and it used to be such that a good deal would possibly be said of it". This youthful creative tour of Santa Teresa, which was once possibly acknowledged to all the youthful members of the family, might also have had some repercussion many years later when one of her brothers, recognized as Agustín de Ahumada, who used to be in the New World seeking his fortune, wrote to the viceroy of Peru. In this letter, dated in Quito on October 25, 1582, he knowledgeable the king's representative in Lima that he was once negotiating with the Royal Audiencia for aid in organizing an day trip of "... up to a hundred men to go in search of a certain province that some residents of this district got here upon which they discovered was once the most populous and richest in gold ever seen; from what they tell of it and the description that they give, one can consider that it must be besides any doubt at all the El Dorado, in the pursuit of which hundreds of leaders and guys have been lost." Like all different such fantasy-inspired will-o'-the-wisps, it used to be so close to at hand that "... in a week of journeying one is there!"

The method of inauguration turned into as soon as started within side the midnight via way of the placing of the candidate under the care of "esquires of honor grave and nicely visible in courtship and nurture and moreover within side the feats of chivalry," who had been to be "governors in all matters regarding him." Under their direction, to start with, a barber shaved him and reduce his hair. He was once then carried out via them to his appointed chamber, wherein a tub tub turned into as soon as prepared hung inner and except with linen and protected with wealthy cloths, into which when they had undressed him he entered. While he turned into within side the bathtub "historic and grave knights" attended him "to inform, train and help him touching the order and feats of chivalry," and after they had fulfilled their challenge they poured a number of the water of the bathtub over his shoulders, signing the left shoulder with the cross, and retired. He turned into then taken from the bathtub and positioned right into a undeniable bed besides hangings, wherein he remained till his body changed into as soon as dry, while the 2 esquires

placed on him a white blouse and over that “a gown of russet with prolonged sleeves having a hood thereto like unto that of an hermit.”

Conclusion

And while the entirety became as soon as organized the prince or venture who become as soon as to knight him came into the hall, and, the candidate’s sword and spurs having been provided to him, he brought the right spur to the “maximum noble and gentle” knight present, and directed him to lock it at the candidate’s proper heel, which he kneeling on one knee and placing the candidate’s proper foot on his knee as a consequence did, signing the candidate’s knee with the cross, and in like way by using any different “noble and gentle” knight the left spur changed into as soon as established to his left heel. And then he who was once to create the knight took the sword and girded him with it, after which embracing him he lifted his proper hand and smote him at the neck or shoulder, saying, “Be thou a pinnacle knight,” and kissed him. When this turned into executed all of them went to the chapel with an lousy lot music, and the brand new knight laying his proper hand at the altar promised to resource and guard the church, and ungirding his sword offered it at the altar. And as he came out from the chapel the hold close put together dinner awaited him on the door and claimed his spurs as his fee, and said, “If you perform a little issue opposite to the order of chivalry (which God forbid), I shall hack the spurs out of your heels.”

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